

The Concept of *Strîdhana* in Ancient and Modern Indian Laws: An Analysis

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The word *strîdhana* is constructed of two words i.e., *strî* and *dhana*. The term *strî* stands for woman and *dhana* denotes property. So, the word *strîdhana* implies the property related to woman. The gift which a woman receives during marriage from her husband and parents, is known as *strîdhana* in the texts of Sm[tiúâstras such as *Nâradasm[ti*, *Yâjòavalkyasm[ti* etc. This *strîdhana* was mainly the movable properties viz., clothes, jewelry and other valuable gifts. It is noticed that the legal right of Hindu women to inherent property has been restricted in Indian patriarchal society in ancient times. The only property which women were given was *strîdhana*. But after the establishment of many schools of Hindu Law viz., *Mitâkcarâ* school, *Dâyabhâga* school etc., women used to get more property rights to some extent. The Indian Constitution is also seen to pay noticeable attention to this subject. In this proposed paper a discussion will be prepared on the property rights of Hindu woman both in the ancient and modern Indian laws.

The methodology to be used here is purely analytical and comparative. The data are collected on the basis of various sources received from the desk study.

Keywords: *Strîdhana*, Propertyright, Sm[tiúâstras, Hindu Act.